

BRUNEL UNIVERSITY

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

In 2018-2019, there were 165 higher education institutions (HEIs) in the UK. A report on a survey by Universities UK (UUK)¹ in 2019 found that 81% of HEIs had recently provided improved support for student reporting. In June 2021, campaign group 'Reclaim the Campus'² published a report examining policies on sexual harassment at 40 UK universities, finding that only 13 of the universities had specific sexual misconduct policies. As there is no current legislation focused on GBV for the higher education (HE) sector, a voluntary approach is in place for institutions to implement guidance in the form of policies and recommendations for change.

The Equality Act 2010 drove the implementation of some policies for people with 'protected characteristics', which include sex, sexual orientation, and gender reassignment. More recently, the Office for Students (OfS) (the regulator for HE in England) published a 'Statement of Expectations',³ which is designed to provide a 'set of consistent recommendations to support higher education providers ... to prevent and respond to incidents of harassment and sexual misconduct'. This Statement is not monitored or requiring of registration, and the OfS cannot intervene or provide resolution or redress related to individual student cases and complaints (which must be dealt with through universities' internal complaints and disciplinary procedures) or constitute a regulatory requirement. Nevertheless, this Statement is a cause for institutional change. Though there have been reviews of individual universities following highly publicised sexual misconduct cases, no sanctions have been imposed and there is no oversight of the implementation of recommended change.

¹ <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/topics/equality-diversity-and-inclusion/survey-demonstrates-positive-university>

² <https://www.reclaimthecampus.com/the-reclaim-report>

³ <https://www.officeforstudents.org.uk/advice-and-guidance/student-wellbeing-and-protection/prevent-and-address-harassment-and-sexual-misconduct/statement-of-expectations/>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

Brunel University has a set of five institutional policies which is a mix of dedicated GBV policies and more general policies that address GBV. The Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy is the one that focuses on GBV. The other policies include: Dignity at Work (Bullying and Harassment), a policy for employees; the Relationships at Work Policy and Guidelines; the Bullying and Harassment Policy, which is the overarching policy for students; and the Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Policy about employment. The Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy applies to the whole university community, including students, staff, contractors, suppliers, and visitors and is a university 'owned' policy. The remainder of the policies reviewed are 'owned' by Human Resources and are overseen by Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) teams (students and staff) with direct support provided by the Student Support and Welfare Team on student issues.

URLs

- › Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy: <https://www.brunel.ac.uk/about/administration/policy?id=52585b3f-4799-4402-97c3-98348cd0c463>
- › Dignity at Work: <https://www.brunel.ac.uk/about/administration/equality-and-diversity/documents/pdf/Dignity-at-Work-Policy-Bullying-and-Harassment-final.pdf>
- › Relationships at Work Policy and Guidelines: <https://students.brunel.ac.uk/documents/Policies/relationships-at-work.pdf>
- › Bullying and Harassment Policy: <https://www.brunel.ac.uk/life/supporting-you/documents/pdf/Bullying-and-Harassment-Policy.-December-2019.-Final-docx.pdf>
- › EDI Policy: <https://students.brunel.ac.uk/documents/Policies/equality-and-diversity-policy.pdf>

Entry into force: The Relationships at Work Policy and Guidelines entered into force in 2017, the Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Policy in 2018, and the three other policies in 2019.

TRAINING

Four policies include training on GBV among their measures. The Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy states that training for university employees on responding to disclosures of sexual violence and sexual harassment is highly recommended for all staff and a full-day programme is delivered by Student Services. In addition, information on sexual violence and sexual harassment is provided in the Dignity at Work workshop for employees. Dignity at Work states that employees will be made aware of the acceptable standards of behaviour and the policy through the university's compliance training programme. Bespoke and ad hoc training on Dignity at Work can also be provided to departments/teams by the Human Resources Department. The Bullying and Harassment Policy states that training for the whole university community on preventing and responding to bullying and harassment is highly recommended and is delivered by the Staff and Student Equality and Diversity Managers or on their behalf. Training for students is under development. It is of vital importance that all staff and students know what behaviour is inappropriate and what is expected of them. The EDI policy has in its objectives to deliver the mandatory 'Equally Different' training and refresher training.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

An example of how the university develops knowledge related to GBV and contributes to prevention within the institution is the presentation ‘Tackling Sexual Harassment and Violence in Higher Education’⁴ as a follow-on from the EU, “Universities Supporting Victims of Sexual Violence” (USV react) project led by Brunel University. Other examples include educational materials and learning opportunities for students that deal with consent and other relevant topics⁵.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The five policies combined cover the following **seven** forms of violence: physical violence, psychological violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, stalking, and online violence. The Bullying and Harassment Policy for students covers all seven of these forms of GBV, while Dignity at Work for employees covers six (not sexual violence) and the Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy covers five (not physical and psychological violence). The Relationships at Work Policy focuses on sexual violence and sexual and gender-based harassment. Finally, the EDI Policy does not specify the forms of GBV.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The five policies combined cover **all 7Ps**. Both Dignity at Work and the Bullying and Harassment Policy address the same 5Ps: prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, and provision of services. The Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy addresses 5Ps: all except protection and partnership. Relationships at Work focuses on 3Ps: protection, prosecution, and policy, while the EDI Policy covers the 3Ps: prevention, protection, and partnership. The EDI Policy is the only policy that addresses partnership and the Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy and Relationships at Work Policy are the only ones that address policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

⁴ <http://book.publicpolicyexchange.co.uk/events/JA15-PPE>
⁵ <https://brunelstudents.com/representation/campaigns/sexualhealthweek/>

Target groups: All policies combined address all target groups, which are academic staff, non-academic staff, and students, and they identify other groups, which include contractors, suppliers, visitors, agency workers, honorary appointees, and volunteers.

Specific vulnerable groups: All the policies combined address the following **nine protected characteristics and sex/gender groups** as particularly vulnerable to GBV: staff and students with disabilities, staff and students with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds, LGBTQIA+ staff and students, staff with temporary contracts, new and expecting mothers, and other groups.

Both the Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy and Relationships at Work Policy address seven of these characteristics, except for students with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds, and staff with temporary contracts. Dignity at Work focuses on staff and thus addresses the following four groups: staff with disabilities, staff with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds, LGBTQIA+ staff, and 'other' groups. The EDI Policy addresses four as well: the same three groups as Dignity at Work and staff with temporary contracts. The Bullying and Harassment Policy focuses on students and thus addresses the following five groups: students with disabilities, students with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds, LGBTQIA+ students, new and expecting mothers, and 'other' groups. The documents specifically mention everyone who is covered under the 'protected characteristics' of the Equality Act. The purpose of the policy is to promote equality and fairness, and not to discriminate on the grounds of age, disability, gender reassignment, marriage and civil partnership, pregnancy, maternity, race, religion or belief, sex, or sexual orientation. It also recognises that individuals with intersecting social and cultural characteristics, e.g., gender, disability, LGBT, religion, and different ethnic groups, are potentially more vulnerable to sexual violence and sexual harassment and may require additional support.

Intersectionality addressed: Yes. The Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy gives examples of social and cultural characteristics that may intersect as gender, disability, LGBT, religion, and different ethnic groups. It does not state that the policy is limited to these.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. All documents except the Relationships at Work policy address bystanders. All four documents encourage witnesses to use the relevant reporting mechanisms. The Bullying and Harassment Policy for students emphasises the need for confidentiality for witnesses and that a breach of confidentiality could lead to disciplinary action. The Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy also states: 'In addition an employee, another student or a visitor may observe an incident of sexual violence or sexual harassment and be unsure how to intervene. If someone shares an incident of sexual violence and / or harassment that they have experienced, it is best to respond in the following way:

- › Reply in good faith on the basis that they are telling the truth;
- › Do not make any assumptions – there are many myths within society that lead to victim blaming and it is best to listen non-judgementally;
- › Direct them to specialist services either on or off campus;
- › Do not act without their consent unless the individual or others are still at risk, or they need urgent medical attention.'

There is also mention of the 'bystander effect'. The policy states: 'All members of the University community have a responsibility to take action if they observe sexual violence or sexual harassment as long it is safe to do so. It is important to avoid the bystander effect where the presence of others often discourages individuals from intervening. This can potentially normalise these behaviours and make inappropriate behaviour more acceptable.'

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes. The Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy defines an indicator related to collecting the number of incidences. Further details are not provided.

Monitoring: Yes. All the policies, except for the Relationships at Work Policy, address monitoring. They all deal with the number of incidences or the number of complaints.

Evaluation: Yes. The EDI Policy addresses evaluation. An impact assessment of the EDI Policy is planned to be carried out and a report submitted annually to the Equal Opportunities and Human Resources Committee, which is to include an analysis of data on staff composition, promotions, recruitment, and leavers to show trends and highlight any key issues. Some results relating to protected groups are presented in the annual equality and diversity reporting. There are no statistics relating to monitoring GBV.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

All policies except for the Relationships at Work Policy set out a step-by-step institutional procedure for reporting and investigation. The Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy sets out two different procedures, one for students and one for staff. Dignity at Work targets only staff, gives initial steps, and refers to another complaint/grievance policy. The Bullying and Harassment Policy addresses students and covers violence between students but also between students and staff. The EDI Policy only focuses on violence between staff members.

The Bullying and Harassment Policy does not provide any procedural details; these can be found on the 'report and support' portal.⁶ The EDI Policy defines who to contact and the responsible persons/units. Both the Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy and Dignity at Work sets out the same procedural details: who to contact, how to report, and the responsible persons/units.

EDI Policy

Who to contact: The policy states that employees may wish to seek advice from one of the university's Anti-Harassment Advisers, their HR Business Partner, or the Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Partner. Any concerns should be raised at the earliest opportunity and will be kept confidential. If an employee has a concern or complaint about discrimination, which could be something that they have experienced or witnessed, they should raise this with their line manager in the first instance unless the matter relates to their manager, in which case the next level of management should be approached.

⁶ <https://reportandsupport.brunel.ac.uk/>

Responsible persons/units: The university's Anti-Harassment Advisers, the HR Business Partner, or the Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Partner.

Sexual Violence and Sexual Harassment Policy and Dignity at Work

Who to contact: These policies advise students and staff to contact the Student Support and Welfare Team and an Anti-Harassment Advisor. They also invite students to seek advice or discuss the matter with a personal tutor or lecturer in the college and / or anyone else with whom they feel comfortable, and invite staff to seek advice or discuss the matter with their line manager or a colleague or anyone else with whom they feel comfortable; this could even be a trade union representative. The policies also advise calling the police, the university Security, the HR Business Partner, or the Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Team.

How to report: Reporting can be done in different ways, by phone, e-mail, or via the Report and Support Portal, where a person can disclose their personal details or make an anonymous report.

Responsible persons/units: Human Resources, overseen by an Equality and Diversity Manager.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Kate Clayton-Hathway in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

